

SEDIMENTOLOGICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF THE NIGERIAN TAR SAND DEPOSITS IN PARTS OF SOUTHWESTERN NIGERIA.

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ABSTRACT

Particle size distribution of some Afowo tar sands as well as mineralogical and bitumen saturation analyses were carried out with the aim of elucidating the sedimentological properties of the deposits. Fifty samples of tar sands of the Afowo Formation in parts of south western Nigeria were subjected to granulometric and petrological analyses to determine the particle size distribution as well as other textural characteristics. Three of the samples were analyzed for phase identification using Phillips PW 1050 diffractometer equipped with Cu X-ray source and operated at 40kV and 30Ma.

The results of sedimentological and particle size distribution studies showed that the sands are medium grained, moderately sorted and mesokurtic. The grain morphology can be described as having low to high sphericity, with shapes generally sub-angular to sub-rounded indicating a fairly long period of transportation. Result of x- ray diffraction analysis of the sediments showed that silica is the dominant mineral with traces of hematite and other minerals such as staurolite. Result of the bitumen analyses indicate that the tar sand deposits have an average bitumen saturation of 22.1%.

KEY WORDS- Petrological, Granulometrical, Tar-sands, Sedimentological, Sorting and Grain-size

INTRODUCTION

The Dahomey basin (Fig. 1) is a marginal pull- apart basin (Klemme, 1975) or Margin sag basin (Kingston et al., 1983), which was initiated during the Early Cretaceous separation of African and South American lithospheric plates.

Occurrence of seepage and tar sand deposits over the Okitipupa ridge in the Dahomey basin provided the initial impetus for oil exploration in Nigeria. From the turn of 19th century up till date, no less than over twenty groups comprising public and private ventures have shown degrees of interest in the exploration and exploitation of the deposits.

The occurrence of these deposits has been known since early last century, however, intense investigations only commenced from mid 70's till now. The pioneering efforts were initiated by the Geological Consultancy Unit of the University of Ife (now Obafemi Awolowo University). The geology of these deposits, oil saturation and reserve estimates as well as textural characteristics of the associated sands have been described (Adegoke et al., 1980, and 1981; Enu, 1987). The physicochemical properties of the bitumen in relation to production and processing have been studied (Oshinowo et al., 1982; Ekweozor, 1985; Oluwole et al., 1985). The origin of the bitumen has been discussed (Coker, 1990; Ekweozor, 1986). Other relevant studies on the deposit and geology of the basin include works done by Ako et. al (1983); Ekweozor (1986 and 1990); Ekweozor and Nwachukwu (1989); Enu (1987, 1990); Enu and Adegoke (1984); Elueze and Nton, (2004) and Akinmosin, (2005). These works have highlighted relevant aspects of the geochemical and sedimentological characteristic of the deposit.

This paper is however based on detailed studies of 50 surface tar sand samples which is aimed at updating the sedimentological characteristics of the deposits.

FIG. 1: East-West geological section showing the Dahomey Basin and upper part of the Niger Delta (After Whiteman, 1982).

Fig. 2: Location Map of the Study Area Showing Tar Sands Outcrop Points.

STRATIGRAPHY OF THE DAHOMEY BASIN

The study area lies between latitudes 6°30' to 6°35' N and longitudes 4°30' to 6°45' E and falls within the eastern Dahomey Basin (Fig. 2). The work of Omatsola and Adegoke (1981) on the Cretaceous stratigraphy of the Dahomey basin has recognized three formations belonging to the Abeokuta Group. These are: the Ise Formation, consisting essentially of continental sands, grits and siltstones, overlying the basement complex unconformably. Neocomian to Albian age has been assigned to this formation. Overlying the Ise Formation is the Afowo Formation, which consists of coarse to medium-grained sandstones with variable interbeds of shales, siltstones and clay. The sediments of this formation were deposited in a transitional to marginal marine environment. Turonian to Maastrichtian age has been assigned to this formation. The Araromi Formation consists essentially of sand, overlain by dark-grey shales and

interbedded limestone and marls with occasional lignite bands. The formation conformably overlies the Afowo Formation and Maastrichtian to Paleocene age has been assigned (Omatsola and Adegoke, 1981).

Table 1: Summary of grain size analysis.

Sample No	Grain Size (mean)		Sorting/Standard Deviation		Skewness		Kurtosis	
	Result	Interpretation	Result	Interpretation	Result	Interpretation	Result	Interpretation
A1	0.76	Coarse sand	0.78	Moderately Sorted	-0.11	Near symmetrical	1.04	Mesokurtic
A2	0.25	Medium grained	1.83	Poorly Sorted	-0.13	Near symmetrical	0.90	Mesokurtic
A3	1.53	Medium grained	1.15	Poorly Sorted	-0.09	Near symmetrical	1.16	Leptokurtic
B1	1.83	Medium grained	0.94	Moderately Sorted	-0.02	Near symmetrical	0.99	Mesokurtic
E1	1.43	Medium grained	1.03	Moderately Sorted	-0.03	Near symmetrical	1.05	Mesokurtic
E2	0.82	Coarse sand	0.79	Moderately Sorted	0.00	Near symmetrical	1.04	Mesokurtic
E3	1.26	Medium grained	0.96	Moderately Sorted	0.31	Strongly Fine skewed	1.08	Mesokurtic
E5	1.00	Medium grained	0.73	Moderately Sorted	-0.02	Near symmetrical	1.03	Mesokurtic
E4	0.27	Medium grained	0.71	Moderately Well Sorted	0.05	Near symmetrical	1.02	Mesokurtic
F3	1.44	Medium grained	0.62	Moderately Well Sorted	0.04	Near symmetrical	0.74	Mesokurtic
F4	1.48	Medium grained	0.54	Moderately Well Sorted	-0.09	Near symmetrical	1.2	Leptokurtic
G1	0.82	Coarse sand	1.05	Poorly sorted	0.19	Fine skewed	1.16	Leptokurtic
G2	0.46	Coarse sand	0.80	Moderately Sorted	0.14	Fine skewed	1.07	Mesokurtic

Table 2: Summary of percentage composition of minerals

Sample	Quartz	Biotite	Muscovite	Accessory
A1	99	-	-	1
A3	99.5	-	-	0.5
A6	98	-	1	1
A11	99	-	-	1
A13	98	-	-	2
A17	97	-	-	3
A20	95	1	1	3
A22	99	-	-	1
A23	99.5	-	-	0.5
B2	99.2	-	-	0.8
B3	98	-	1.5	0.5
B4	99.2	-	-	0.8
B5	98.5	-	-	1.5
B9	96	-	-	4
B12	98.5	-	1	0.5
B13	98	-	-	2
B24	96	-	-	4
B25	95	1	3	1

Overlying the Abeokuta Group conformably is the Imo Group, which comprises of shale, limestone and marls. The two-lithostratigraphic units under this group are: Ewekoro and Akinbo Formations. Ewekoro Formation consists of thick fossiliferous limestone. Adegoke (1977) described the Ewekoro Formation as consisting of shaly limestone 12.5m thick which tends to be sandy and was divided into three microfacies. Ogbe (1972) however, further modified this and proposed a fourth unit. The four microfacies making up this formation are described as follows: sandy biomicrite, shelly biomicrite, algal biosparite, and red phosphatic biomicrite. Ewekoro Formation is Paleocene in age and is associated with shallow marine environment due to abundance of coralline algae, gastropods, pelecypods, echinoid fragments and other skeletal debris. Akinbo Formation lies on the Ewekoro Formation and it comprises of shale, glauconitic rock bank, and gritty sand which is pure grey in colour and shows little clay. Lenses of limestone from Ewekoro Formation grades laterally into the Akinbo shale very close to the base. The base is characterized by the presence of a glauconitic band. The age of the formation is Paleocene to Eocene.

Table 3: XRD Identified Compounds

Samples	Identified Compound	Remarks
D1	Quartz SiO ₂ Hematite Fe ₂ O ₃	Predominant Traces
P3	Quartz SiO ₂ Staurolite Fe _{3.546} (Al _{17.99} Si ₈ O ₄₅)(OH) ₃	Predominant Possibly present, traces.
P5	Quartz SiO ₂ Hematite Fe ₂ O ₃	Predominant Traces

Table 4: Bitumen Saturation Result

Sample No	Bitumen Saturation	Facies
A1	22.3	Medium grained sandstone
A3	21.0	Medium grained sandstone
A6	29.5	Fine grained sandstone
A11	16.2	Medium grained sandstone
B2	25.0	Fine grained sandstone
B6	20.6	Medium grained sandstone
B11	19.8	Medium grained sandstone

Overlying the Imo Group is the Oshoshun Formation. It is a sequence of mostly pale greenish-grey laminated, phosphatic marls, light grey to white-purple clay with interbeds of sandstones. It also consists of claystone underlain by argillaceous limestones with light grey shale at the bottom. There are inclusions of phosphatic and glauconitic materials in the lower part of the formation and the upper part is made up of medium to coarse-grained silty sandstone (Adegoke, 1969). The formation is Eocene in age (Agagu, 1985). The sedimentation of the Oshoshun Formation was followed by a regression, which deposited the sandstone unit of Ilaro Formation (Kogbe, 1976). The sequence represents mainly coarse sandy estuarine deltaic and continental beds, which show rapid lateral facies change.

The coastal plain sands are the youngest sedimentary unit in the eastern Dahomey basin. It probably overlies the Ilaro Formation unconformably, but convincing evidence as to this is lacking (Jones and Hockey, 1964). It consists of soft, poorly sorted clayey sand and pebbly sands. The age is from Oligocene to Recent.

METHODOLOGY

The outcrops which are located around stream heads and channels were defined based on the nature of the exposure, e.g. springs, channel bank, etc and their extent noted. The outcrops were subsequently studied based on facies change and bed thickness measured with measuring tapes. Outcrop co-ordinates and elevation were taken using a GPS.

Sampling of tar sands was done with the use of a geologic hammer, cutlass, shovel and digger to chip out samples into sample bags made of polythene material. Lithologic logs of the exposed surfaces were drawn to depict the sedimentological characteristics of the outcrops. The various outcrops were equally captured in photographs with a digital camera.

Each sample was properly examined and quality checked. Thereafter, 100g of each sample was weighed using a top loading balance (Fischer brand PF-4001) and soaked in toluene for about 24hours to free the sediment, after which it was washed, dried and re-weighed. The liberated sediments were subsequently taken for the following analyses:

- a. Granulometric analysis, b. Petrographic analysis (Mineralogical composition and Provenance study). Other sedimentological analyses carried out include (Lithofacies Identification, Bitumen saturation and Mineral identification using X-Ray Diffractometric (XRD) technique).

Fig.3: Histograms showing grain size distribution of the sediments

Fifty air dried samples each weighing 100 g were run through a set of mechanical sieves of the following mesh sizes, 1.40mm, 1.0mm, 0.70mm, 0.50mm, 0.35mm, 0.25mm, 0.18mm, 0.13mm, 0.09mm, 0.062mm and Pan which are equivalent of - 0.5, 0.0, 0.5, 1.0, 1.5, 2.0, 2.5, 3.0, 3.5 and 4.0 phi values respectively arranged in order of the coarsest sieve on top and the finest below. This analysis was done with a mechanical shaker agitating for 15 minutes for each sample. The amount, retained on each sieve was then weighed using a sensitive weighing balance. The bottom of the sieve was then cleaned thoroughly but gently with a brush to dislodge the grains partially stacked in the mesh holes to avoid contamination of subsequent samples.

GreenSmith (1978) and Oronsaye (1980) have discussed some constraints of this method, which include errors introduced as a result of sieve apertures not being of constant size and/or grains adhering to the sieves. Inadequate or over sieving and non- standardization of the quantity of sample being sieved are other sources of error inherent in

the sieving method. However, the adoption of 100g of sample and fixed sieving period of about 15 minutes for all samples analyzed are considered effective checks on some of these constraints.

Plate 1: Textural and mineralogical characteristics of the sediments (mag x100)

Plate 2: Textural and mineralogical characteristics of the sediments (mag. X 100)

Plate 3: Quartz varieties showing (quartz with vacuole and re-entrance angle-mag x 100)

The individual weight, cumulative weight as well as individual and cumulative weight percentages were determined to construct histogram, and cumulative frequency curve for each sample on arithmetic graphs and semi log graphs. The necessary phi values i.e. ϕ_5 , ϕ_{16} , ϕ_{25} , ϕ_{50} , ϕ_{75} , ϕ_{84} and ϕ_{95} used for calculation of statistical parameters were obtained from the cumulative frequency curves.

Mineralogical analysis was carried out by preparing slides of 30 selected samples. These slides were viewed under plane polarized and crossed nicols. Minerals present in each of the samples were identified by comparing them with standard mineralogical charts, and their percentage composition estimated. In addition to such minerals like quartz,

feldspars and micas, sands may also contain other detrital minerals which can be referred to as accessory or heavy minerals. This method was adopted because of quartz abundance in the sediments, and its characteristics of high mechanical and chemical stability under any surface condition when subjected to prolong period of sedimentation without losing its form.

The two petrographic approaches were employed for provenance studies are: Quartz varieties determination and heavy mineral assemblage analyses. Based on Krynine genetic classification of quartz types (Krynine 1940), origin of a particular quartz variety can be determined. His classification was based on the following:

i. Extinction (Straight, wavy or undulose extinction)

Plate 4: Photomicrographs of heavy minerals (Mag. x100)

ii. Inclusion (minerals or vacuoles).

iii. Grain shape and contact or boundary relationship

iv. Number of quartz crystal in a sand grain (single or composite grain)

Thirty slides of the prepared samples were examined under petrographic research microscope for quartz varieties determination based on Krynine criteria of classification. Inclusions in quartz crystals may be in form of minerals e.g. feldspar, biotite, trace elements etc. or in form of vacuoles which mostly are trapped in air during crystallization. Space may be left in form of re-entrance angle formed as a result of leaching away of labile or unstable mineral included on the surface of the quartz. Grain shape may be equant, subequant to irregular, stretched or elongated depending on the prevalent factor during crystallization. The composition of monocrystalline quartz in sand grain is often associated with igneous origin while polycrystalline quartz may have either igneous or metamorphic origin.

Heavy minerals are minerals that have specific gravity greater than 2.8. Heavy minerals in any sediment are in a sense the survivors of selective weathering, and they tend to be mostly concentrated within finer grained portions of sediments. Both effects of settling velocity and abrasion tend to concentrate the minerals in the fine-grained portion.

The separating fluid used for this analysis was bromoform with specific gravity of 2.85. The selected 25 samples were screened through a 75 μ m sieve size to obtain uniform grain size. 10g of each of the screened samples was subjected to heavy mineral separation using bromoform. The separated minerals of each sample were later dried and mounted on a glass slide with the aid of Canada balsam (Sato, 1966). Each slide was subsequently viewed under the petrographic microscope and relative abundance of each mineral grain was calculated to give its number

percentage. Generally, each heavy mineral is identified by its colour. The three toughest ultra-stable minerals (i.e. zircon, rutile and tourmaline) were used to calculate the ZTR index of the sediments (i.e. their mineralogical maturity). The ZTR for each of the selected samples was calculated using the formula-

$$\frac{Z+T+R}{\text{Total no of NO}} \times 100$$

Where NO = *Non-opaque*, Z=*Zircon*, T=*Tourmaline* and R=*Rutile*.

*Plate 5: Photomicrographs of heavy minerals (Mag. x100)
(where Z- Zircon, K- kyanite, R- Rutile Si- Sillimanite, S- Staurolite, T- Tourmaline, O- Opaque mineral)*

This formula is referred to as Hubert's (1962) scheme. From the calculated percentage, ZTR<75% implies immature to sub-mature sediments; ZTR>75% indicates mineralogically matured sediments

Provenance study should reveal transportation history of any sedimentary particle. Hence, sediments with well rounded heavy mineral grains indicate a long transportation history. Sediments having rounded tourmaline or zircon for instance, indicate a long transport history and those with angular to sub-angular indicate that such sediments have not traveled too far. Angular and rounded tourmalines seen in the same specimen indicate multiple source areas.

Other sedimentological studies carried out are: Lithofacies Identification and x-ray diffraction analysis. The lithofacies identification was achieved by carrying out whole rock description in the field coupled with visual and binocular microscopic description of collected samples on the basis of the following: i. Rock type, ii. Textural characteristics and iii. Mineralogical composition.

Three samples were analyzed for phase identification. The samples were ground in a ceramic mortar prior to when X-ray diffraction was performed on a pressed portion of each sample using Phillips PW 1050 diffractometer equipped with Cu X-ray source and operated at 40kV and 30Ma (Philips and Philips, 1980).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

From the analyses, sediments of the study area can be seen to be predominantly bimodal, with the major class in the 1.25-2.50 ϕ . Average modal class corresponds to the medium grained sands. An average graphic mean of 0.98 ϕ

was derived for the sands. This indicates that majority of the sands are medium grained. Standard deviation values range between $0.54\phi - 1.83\phi$ (average of 0.92ϕ), meaning that majority of the sands are well sorted. The sediments are largely mesokurtic while others are leptokurtic to platykurtic. Skewness varies over a wide range (positively skewed to strongly coarse skewed).

Histogram plots on some of the results obtained from granulometric analysis are shown in Figure 3a, while summary of the granulometric analysis result is shown in Table 1.

Plate 6: Photomicrograph of a fine-grained sandstone.

Plate 7: Photomicrograph of a medium-grained sandstone.

Grain roundness varies between 0.15 and 0.85 and ranged in shape from sub-angular to sub-rounded, Plates 1 and 2. Compaction is moderate with little or no cementing material. Cementation and authigenic mineral growth are lacking probably due to early bitumen impregnation. The grain morphology viewed under petrological microscope shows low- high sphericity Plates 1 and 2. Quartz is present on average of 95%. They have low relief and show wavy and undulose extinction. They appeared colourless. Brown coloured biotite was observed under cross-polarized light. It is pleochroic and occurs as thin flakes. It constitutes about 2% of the sand content. Muscovite was equally identified constituting about 3%. The result of mineralogical analysis is shown in Table 2.

Provenance

Almost all samples examined under the petrographic microscope for their quartz varieties indicate the type referred to by Krynine (1940) as common quartz. They exhibited xenomorphic or allotriomorphic irregular (anhedral) to subequant shape. They are sometimes with re-entrance angles. Generally, quartz types sometimes

contain no inclusions other than a small amount of randomly scattered vacuoles, which were probably created during crystallization (Plate 3). These quartz types were genetically classified by Krynine (1940) as being plutonic igneous quartz derivable from granite gneiss or a granite batholith. The quartz types show a very significant similarity with the metamorphic quartz type in that their composite grain boundaries are often straight and in addition grains have wide different optic orientation. Euhedral water clear quartz crystals, which are indicative of volcanic source rock, are generally absent.

The percentage of opaque minerals in all the samples constitutes about 50%. Non-opaque minerals identified include: staurolite, tourmaline, rutile, sillimanite, zircon, kyanite, zoisite, epidote, garnet and hornblende. The amount of shape and colour of zircon (being the most ubiquitous and abundant non-opaque heavy mineral in the sediments) show that it predominates and its shapes are only fairly mechanically altered (commonly euhedral to subhedral) due to their high stability and lack of good cleavage. They appear commonly colourless. The proportion of tourmaline is next to that of zircon in nearly all the samples. It is usually brown in colour (sometimes greenish) or brownish yellow. Its shape is commonly euhedral. Rutile is relatively abundant in most samples; only the red coloured variety was recognized. Staurolite, sillimanite and kyanite are equally in small proportion. Photomicrographs of the heavy minerals are shown in Plates 4 and 5. From the ZTR computation indices, average ZTR index calculated is greater than 75%, consequently the sands are said to be mineralogically mature.

Lithofacies and Textural Characteristics

From physical examination and binocular microscopy, two main facies and two sub-facies were established from outcrop sections within the study area. These include:

a. Sandstone facies with two sub-facies- i. Fine-grained sandstone ii. Medium-grained sandstone.

b. Shale facies.

A (i). Fine Grained Sandstone Sub-facies

This facies (Plate 6) occurs mostly at the lower sections below shale sequence in outcrops where identified. This facies contains millimetre scale shale laminae and displays a dark-grey to black colouration in all the outcrops where it was observed. The grain sizes range from very fine to coarse, sub angular to sub rounded grains, they appeared moderately sorted, with mica and carbonaceous materials as accessories.

A (ii). Medium-Grained Sandstone Sub-facies

This sub-facies (Plate 7) was well represented almost in the outcrops. It is black in colour with grain sizes ranging from very fine to very coarse, sub-angular to sub rounded, moderately sorted and consolidated.

B. Shale Lithofacies

This lithofacies occurs in most cases at the lower section of the outcrop where observed. It is basically dark grey and fissile. It is characterized by millimetre scale of very fine to fine grain, and well sorted sand laminae. Mica, pyrite and carbonaceous materials occur as accessories.

X-ray diffraction (XRD) result

The compounds identified in the samples are presented in Table 3. The identified compounds confirm the result of the mineralogical study where quartz has a proportion of over 90% of the total mineralogical composition of the bitumen impregnated sediments.

Bitumen Saturation

Bitumen saturation refers to the wt. % or vol. % bitumen present per unit mass or volume of oil sands. The following categories of oil sands have been identified, Coker, (1988):

i. Rich sands – Sb > 10wt. % (>19.2 vol. %)

ii. Intermediate sands – Sb > 5 to < 10wt. % (9.9 to < 19.2 vol.)

iii. Lean sands – Sb > 2 TO < 5 wt % (>4 to <9.9 vol. %)

Result of the bitumen analysis showed that the tar sand deposits belong to category one (i.e. rich sands) with an average bitumen saturation of 22.1%, Table 4. The degree of saturation was found to be lowest in sediments with poorest sorting, having appreciable quantities of fine. It is therefore expected that those factors will in no doubt influence the bitumen withdrawal efficiency.

SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION

From physical and binocular microscopic examinations, two main and two sub-facies were established from outcrop sections within the study area. These include: Sandstone facies with two sub-facies (fine-grained sandstone and medium-grained sandstone), and shale facies.

The particle size distribution of the deposits as seen in this study varies without a definite pattern. Mostly, the sands are medium grained and moderately sorted with no significant fines. Except for few locations with poor sorting, the bulk of the sediments are moderately sorted. This quality, coupled with insignificant fines content will in no doubt enhance both bitumen saturation and withdrawal efficiency positively.

The sands as observed from the analyses can be characterized as being chemically and mechanically stable with ZTR > 75%. The quartz content on the average is greater than 90% with little or no feldspar. Minor components are mica (biotite and muscovite) and heavy minerals (mostly zircon and tourmaline). These facts were equally confirmed the X-RD analyses. The sub-angular/sub-rounded shapes of the grains coupled with little of fines may be indication of fairly long period of sediments transportation.

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